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² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Deliverable D7.6

Demonstrator: Advanced post-graduate training programme launched

31/05/2019

Executive Summary

More than 20% of the European fishing fleets catches are taken from non-European waters. Access to these waters is often based on agreements with coastal states that allow the EU fleet to fish from surplus stocks in return for financial support. These agreements have been subjected to criticism, as these fisheries are sometimes poorly regulated and management decisions are often based on limited knowledge, compliance, and enforcement capabilities. It is also too often the case that trust between stakeholders is lacking. The aim of the FarFish project is to overcome these hurdles.

The FarFish project is designed around six case study areas in which the European fleet is actively engaged in fishing activities, including Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and Seychelles, as well as the international high-seas areas in the southeast and southwest Atlantic. In this context of geographic, economic and cultural diversity, the project will gain insights into the sustainability of commercially important species.

Significant focus of the FarFish project is placed on education, knowledge transfer, and improving professional skills and competences of stakeholders within the case studies and beyond within the field of fisheries management. This includes education and knowledge transfer to a wide variety of stakeholders within the respective value chains, utilising different means; such as social media, e-learning, Tutor-web, a special university-level certificate program in Marine Management and Innovation and a six-month post-graduate program tailor-made for FarFish. This document reports on the setup and launching of the six-month post-graduate program, which was launched in September 2018 and will graduate at least five students before end of the FarFish project. Two students have already been graduated when this report is published and four more have been invited to join the programme in September 2019.

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Abbreviations

CRODT	Centre de Recherches Océanographique de Dhakar-Thiaroye/Centre for Oceanographic Research of Dakar-Thiaroye
IMROP	The Institut Mauritanien de Recherches Océanographiques et de Peches
INDP	The National Institute for Fisheries Development
ISRA	Institut Sénégalais de Recherches Agricoles/Senegalese Institute of Agricultural Research
OSCM	Ocean Science Centre of Mindelo
SFA	Seychelles Fishing Authority
UNUFTP	United Nations University - Fisheries Training Programme

1 Introduction

More than 20% of the European fishing fleets catches are taken from non-European waters. Access to these waters is often based on agreements with coastal states that allow the EU fleet to fish from surplus stocks in return for financial support. These agreements have been subjected to criticism, as these fisheries are sometimes poorly regulated and management decisions are often based on limited knowledge, compliance, and enforcement capabilities. It is also too often the case that trust between stakeholders is lacking. The aim of the FarFish project is to overcome these hurdles.

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UNUFTP organises the six-month post-graduate programme, where people already working within the case study areas in influential positions can get training and in-depth knowledge on fisheries management. These students do then, after completing the programme, return to their positions in their home country where the knowledge is applied, and the students/fellows can even disseminate their knowledge to co-workers.

This part of the FarFish project is then intended to end with an in-country workshop in a selected case study country, where the target audience and topics will be subject to the training need assessment and the work conducted during the six-month training program.

2 The advance post-graduate training programme

The advance post-graduate training described in Task 7.5 was launched in September 2018, and the first round of training was completed in March 2019. Based upon the training needs assessments (D7.4), three candidates were invited to attend the six-month training programme run annually through the UNUFTP. Of these, two were from INDP in Cabo Verde, and one was from CRODT in Senegal. Due to institutional barriers, the candidate from CRODT was not able to attend the training.

3 Graduated research fellows – Class of 2019

On March 12th 2019, UNUFTP celebrated the graduation of its 21st cohort of research fellows participating in the annual six-month post-graduate training in Iceland. This year, UNUFTP was pleased to welcome two fellows from Cabo Verde as part of its work relating to capacity building within the FarFish project. Both research fellows were selected through the FarFish training needs assessment work conducted at Instituto Nacional de Desenvolvimento das Pescas (INDP) in Mindelo, Cabo Verde last year. Through the training needs assessments at INDP, it was established that stock assessment was a priority area for building institutional capacity, and both fellows specialised on that line of study while in Iceland.

One of the UNUFTP fellows from INDP selected to participate in the six-month training was Mr. Nuno Vieira. Nuno is a biologist and ocean specialist with the INDP and the Ocean Science Centre of Mindelo (OSCM). His research with the UNUFTP related to a recent decline in the stock of mackerel scad, a small pelagic fish with significant economic importance to the Cabo Verdean economy. Nuno's study aimed to determine if the decline in catches in recent years could be better attributed to fishing pressure or environmental factors. The results of his research will have clear implications on how the stock is managed in the future. The abstract from Nuno's thesis/work can be seen in the appendix and the full text will be made available shortly on the UNUFTP and FarFish websites.

Another UNUFTP fellow from INDP selected to participate in the six-month training through the FarFish project was Ms. Aliciany da Luz. Aliciany is a marine biologist working at INDP in Mindelo. Her research conducted through the UNU-FTP related to the creation of an age-length key for the blackspot picarel, an important species in the artisanal sector in Cabo Verde. Though INDP had collected otoliths from the blackspot picarel for several years, these samples had never been analysed. Aliciany took on the ambitious task to analyse otoliths from 134 specimens and along the way, create a procedure which will guide the ageing of similar samples in the future. The abstract from Aliciany's thesis/work can be seen in the appendix and the full text will be made available shortly on the UNUFTP and FarFish websites.

Now that Alicainy and Nuno have successfully completed the training, they have returned to Cabo Verde and INDP, where they are better equipped to contribute new scientific knowledge to the institution's stock assessment unit. On May 30, 2019, Nuno and Aliciany presented their work to their colleagues through a seminar at INDP. The seminar was attended by the Cabo Verde Case Study Leader in FarFish and the FarFish Work Package 7 leader.

4 Invited research fellows – Class of 2020

Based on the training needs assessment, four candidate research fellows have been invited to join the programme starting in September 2019, these are from CRODT/ISRA (Senegal), IMROP (Mauritania), SFA (Seychelles) and INDP (Cape Verde). When this report is published it looks like all of these fellows will be able to accept the offer.

5 Next steps

According to the plan it looks as FarFish will manage to graduate six fellows by mid-year 2020, which means that the project will have completed what was set out to do in this task of the project. The aim then will be to activate the fellows in sharing the knowledge among co-workers, contribute to other task in the project and last, but not least, to take part in an in-country workshop in a selected case study country, where the target audience and topics will be subject to the training need assessment and the work conducted during the six-month training program.

6 Appendixes

6.1 Abstract of Mr. Nuno Vieira thesis

Fisheries are one of the most important economic activities in Cabo Verde, employing 8,600 people, representing 4 % of the economically active population. The fisheries in Cabo Verdean waters are divided into two components: artisanal and industrial. The small pelagic and the tuna fisheries are some of the most important fisheries in Cabo Verde. Of the small pelagic, the mackerel scad has social and economic importance and it is used as bait, food and in the canning industry. Official landing data from INDP during the period from 1989 to 2015 indicates that mackerel scad made up almost 40 % of Cabo Verdean total catches at the peak of its fishery in 1997 and 1998. After this peak the catch has decreased significantly, especially in the last six years, representing only 6.6 % of the landing in 2015 an amount of 642 tonnes.

The main goal of this study was to assess if the fluctuations and recent decline in mackerel scad catch in Cape Verdeans waters are caused by harvesting or by changes in environmental parameters. The data analysed was provided by reconstructed catch data during the time frame 1950 to 2014 from the research initiative Sea Around Us, official landing and effort data from INDP over the period from 1989 to 2015, biological data from INDP over the period 1989 to 2018, and in addition, sea surface temperature and chlorophyll-a from satellite observation.

The growth parameters K and L_{∞} , the recruitment pattern and the total mortality were computed in the software FISAT II, the biomass was estimated by the Shaefer model using the Sea Around Us reconstructed catch data and CPUE data from INDP for both fleet, and simple linear regression was applied to see the correlation between the catch data and the environmental parameters. The growth parameters computed from FISAT II indicate $L_{\infty} = 40.6$ cm, $K = 0.450$ year⁻¹, $Z = 3.32$ year⁻¹, $F = 2.31$ year⁻¹, $M = 0.92$ year⁻¹.

The biomass estimated by the Shaefer model indicate an MSY of 5,619 tonnes using the Sea Around Us catch and artisanal CPUE from INDP, and 5,686 tonnes using the Sea Around Us catch and industrial CPUE from INDP, the correlation between catch and environmental parameters, showed an $R^2 = 0.043$ when catch is correlated with sea surface temperature, and $R^2 = 0.21$ when catch is correlated with chlorophyll-a. There are indicators that the stock is declining but is not very conclusive, hence the fishing effort should be reduced until more information is known. The stock did not show strong link to the environmental factors, further studies and improved sampling procedures need to be done in order to get more information on the stock.

6.2 Abstract of Ms. Alicainy da Luz thesis

Blackspot picarel (*Spicara melanurus*) is a fish species from the Sparidae family and is an important species for the artisanal fishery in Cape Verde. Despite being commercially important, stock assessment is not performed for this species due to limited knowledge of life story traits and for lacking methodology to investigate age of the species. In this study, methodology to estimate age of blackspot picarel from Cape Verde waters was investigated by counting otolith increments and by measuring otolith size. Otoliths from 134 specimen ranging in fork length from 4.5 cm to 29 cm were analysed. Increments became visible once the otolith was sectioned, polished, image taken and the image enhanced. An age-length key was produced. Precision of the ageing method was estimated by replicating increment count for 23% of otoliths. For replicas, the mean coefficient of variation was 8.76% which is acceptable. The maximum age estimated was 17 years and the von Bertalanffy growth parameters were $L_{\infty}=36.17$ cm, $k=0.09$ [year]⁻¹, $t_0=0.89$ year. This suggests that blackspot picarel is a slow-growing and a long-lived species. Maturity-at-age was 7.1 year. The relationship between specimen length and otolith dimension, and between specimen age and otolith dimensions was strong and explained 89% or more of variance in otolith dimensions. The age-length key, maturity-at-age, and growth rate provide vital information for stock assessment.